

What may be a table in education research?

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Tabular representation of information can be traced to ancient times. They were and are used in a wide variety of ways. While every table is essentially a list, their interpretation varies from the simpler to the very complex. This aspect is explored in some detail by the present author. Based on the considerations, she suggests a number of ways of improving the study of tables in the classroom. Possible ideas of pedagogic consistency in the identification of difficulty of table use, and reduction of math anxiety are also touched upon.

Introduction

In this research, by a table will be meant any finite sequence of n -tuples that has been represented in table-form with at least two columns. This preliminary restriction is intended to avoid arbitrary finite sequences of things that can also be regarded as trivial tables.

Tables are everywhere, they have been used to keep records of transactions, record observations, facilitate calculations, represent arithmetic and algebraic operations and also to retrieve information. Babylonian multiplication tables on clay tablets are among the earliest tables in recorded history. Though lists containing information about pairs or triples of entities such as records of transactions go back to earlier times, tables for information are only a few centuries old.

Over the last few decades, tables have been put to far more interesting and complex uses across diverse disciplines. They have evolved radically in relation to representation, use, storage, retrieval, exploration, reasoning, and visualization. From a pedagogical perspective, they are taken for granted in the study of most subjects. Subjects such as computer science and statistics are relatively table-intensive, but comprehension of tables is assumed to be a matter of routine learning. Storage, retrieval, and related optimization problems are central to the study of databases from a machine, algorithmic, and software perspective. In most areas of soft computing, knowledge discovery from databases, and formal approaches to vagueness such as rough sets, tables are studied in different perspectives at considerable depth.

Despite such diversity in the interpretation and use of tables, they are not commonly explored from broader perspectives in school curricula, and only a handful of studies on related education research are known. When they are studied as in introductory chapters on statistics, the focus is usually on other aspects of the subject. In fact tables can be used to hide information from those without the skills or the time to read them. It is also known that difficulty with multiplication tables contributes to math anxiety or vice versa (Dowker et al., 2016; Luttenberger et al., 2018).

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In this research, aspects of the origin and use of tables are considered from a critical perspective, and a case is made for teaching about diverse interpretations and use of tables at different levels of learning. Further it is argued that an improved, broader approach to tables may help in reducing math anxiety of learners and teachers.

Tables for algebras, logic, and calculation

Tables for interpreting operations on a fixed finite set and those for calculation over the real numbers have certain similarities despite the relatively abstract nature of the former. However, they are used in diverse ways in universal/abstract algebra, logic, and related fields.

The interpretation of unary and binary operations on a finite set (that is reasonably small) can be easily represented as a table. But the actual properties satisfied by the algebra may not be directly readable from the table. Typically, tables play a complementary role in the study of abstract algebras. For example, a groupoid operation on the set $S = \{a, b, c\}$ can be represented by Table 1.

\odot	a	b	c
a	a	c	c
b	b	b	a
c	a	b	c

Table 1: A groupoid

This way of representing operations is similar to that of multiplication tables in arithmetic (which is loosely taught as a partial algebra in schools in the present author's view).

Tables and graph theory

While every table can also be represented as a labeled graph satisfying certain properties in principle, such representation may be seen to be obscuring or sometimes improving the essential information present in a table. Further, a table can potentially be represented in non-unique ways using graphs based on perspective.

Graphs in turn are representable as relational systems, multi-sorted total algebras and single-sorted partial algebras (see Alberich et al., 1994; Chajda et al., 2015; Mani & Radeleczki, 2020). So the connection between tables and partial algebras capture related ontological content to an extent (from a mereo-ontological perspective as in Burkhardt et al. 2017). It may be noted that these are distinct from the multi-dimensional ontologies of math/statistical education research as for example in Pino-Fan et al. (2015) that do not refer to tables in a significantly different way.

Truth tables in logic

Some logics admit of truth tables or generalizations thereof. Set-valued valuations in particular can be used to handle relatively indeterministic situations (as in nmatrices). Truth tables in logic can be written for each logical operation/connective on a set of truth values (as for algebraic operations) or can also be interpreted by substitution when they are written schematically.

An example for the latter form for classical propositional logic is shown in Table 2 q and s need to be substituted by suitable sentences (built in accordance with formation rules) before reading from the table. Thus, for a given sentence q_0 with truth value 0 (false) and a sentence s_0 with truth value 1 (true), it follows that $s_0 \& q_0$ has truth value 0 from the table. This method does not explicitly assume set theoretic axioms or that the collection of all admissible formulas form a set. For details, the reader may refer to Magnus et al. (2020).

s	q	$s \& q$	$s \vee q$	$s \rightarrow q$	$s \leftrightarrow q$
1	1	1	1	1	1
1	0	0	1	0	0
0	1	0	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	1	1

Table 2: Truth table for PC connectives

Semantic tableaux or truth-trees are also used in proof theory and concern derivations using a method of breaking-down formulas to atomic ones. They can be used to check satisfiability of modal formulas, for decision procedures and proofs. Though these can be interpreted as tables regulated by rules, the connection is rather weak.

Tables for astronomical calculations

Tables for the purpose of computation have been extensively employed in positional astronomy for over 5000 years. The starting point of related geometric/physical models is the geocentric celestial sphere (Figure 1). Points on the surface of the sphere are mapped to positions of all stars, planets and other observable astronomical bodies. Further it is assumed that the abstract sphere rotates relative to the Earth along the North-South pole axis among other things. To represent points on the sphere, additional circles called the celestial equator (corresponding to an extension of the equatorial diameter) or the ecliptic (corresponding to positions of the Sun on a great circle) are used. Other local coordinate systems dependent on the position of the observer on the Earth have also been employed. All these required extensive use of special purpose trigonometric tables before the advent of logarithm based computations.

An example of a table of sines, and tangents that dates to early sixteenth century (due to Regiomontanus; Rosenfield, 1988; Zinner, 1990) is presented in Figure 2. It may be noted this is part of the earliest systematic treatise on trigonometry.

Figure 1: Celestial sphere (adapted from <http://www.hps.cam.ac.uk/starry/mathtechnique/queslrg.jpg>)

The computation is not likely to be obvious to a modern reader because its use involves a few steps.

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Circuli Argandi Vert.		Equatio Centri.		Distantia pericentri.		Distantia Diurni.		Equatio Argometri.		Circulus minutus.		Equatio Centri.		Distantia pericentri.		Distantia Diurni.		Equatio Argometri.		Circulus minutus.		Circuli Argandi Vert.			
g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m	g	m
0	0	12	0	26	2	16	4	24	54	24	13	4	43	2	31	4	27	0	2	13	9	22	55		
0	10	12	1	16	2	16	4	24	54	24	13	4	43	2	31	4	26	17	0	2	13	9	22		
0	20	12	2	16	2	16	4	24	54	24	13	4	43	2	31	4	26	14	2	24	9	18	55		
0	30	12	3	16	2	16	4	24	54	24	13	4	43	2	31	4	25	20	0	2	13	9	22		
0	40	12	4	16	2	16	4	24	54	24	13	4	43	2	30	4	25	26	0	2	13	9	22		
0	50	12	5	16	2	17	4	25	10	0	13	3	43	2	30	4	25	2	0	2	13	9	22		
1	0	12	6	17	2	17	4	25	18	0	13	3	43	2	30	4	24	38	0	2	13	9	22		
1	10	12	7	17	2	17	4	25	22	0	13	3	43	2	30	4	24	14	0	2	13	9	22		
1	20	12	8	17	2	17	4	25	25	0	13	2	43	2	30	4	23	20	0	2	13	9	22		
1	30	12	9	17	2	17	4	25	28	0	13	2	43	2	30	4	23	26	0	2	13	9	22		
1	40	12	10	17	2	17	4	25	31	0	13	2	43	2	29	4	23	1	0	2	13	9	22		
1	50	12	11	17	2	18	4	25	34	0	13	1	43	2	29	4	22	16	0	2	13	9	22		
2	0	12	12	17	2	18	4	25	37	0	12	13	4	29	4	22	11	0	2	13	9	22			
2	10	12	11	17	2	18	4	25	39	0	12	13	4	29	4	21	16	0	2	13	9	22			

Figure 2: Trigonometric Tables, 1533 CE (adapted from www.hps.cam.ac.uk/starry)

The Rudolphine Tables (see Figure 3) due to Tycho Brahe and Johann Kepler (Swerdlow, 2000) that was published in 1627 permitted calculations (for the first time) of planetary positions at any given time in the past or future. The original book can be accessed from this web page: <https://dibiki.uni-kiel.de/viewer/resolver?urn=urn:nbn:de:gbv:8:2-1636149>.

64 Tabularum Rudolphi

Tabula Aequationum MARTIS.

Anomalia Eccentri. Cum aequatione in parte phys.	Intervallum Cum Logarithm.	Anomalia conparata.	Intervallū Cum Logarithm.	Anomalia Eccentri. Cum aequatione in parte phys.	Intervallum Cum Logarithm.	Anomalia conparata.	Intervallū Cum Logarithm.
110 4.55.50	1100 1. 5.36	115.17.11	145293 17317	150 2.39.14	16210 1.10.35	147.13.44	140157 13713
111 4.11. 1	1110 1. 5.47	116.19.52	145030 17211	151 2.34.23	16410 1.10.43	148.18.42	140005 13651
112 4.10. 6	1120 1. 5.59	117.22.39	144871 17067	152 2.29.39	16480 1.10.49	149.23.44	139887 13566
113 4.27. 8	1130 1. 6.11	118.25.31	144663 16924	153 2.24.51	16750 1.10.56	150.28.49	139773 13484
114 4.24. 2	1140 1. 6.22	119.28.29	144458 16782	154 2.10.14	16910 1.11. 3	151.33.57	139662 13406
115 4.20.51	1150 1. 6.34	120.31.33	144255 16642	155 2.14.39	17060 1.11.10	152.39. 9	139558 13313
116 4.17.40	1160 1. 6.46	121.34.42	144055 16503	156 2. 9.30	17210 1.11.16	153.44.23	139456 13257
117	1170 1. 6.58		143857	157	17350		139357

Figure 3: Rudolphine Tables, 1627CE

These tables were relatively accurate to 10 seconds, optimized on Kepler's elliptical heliocentric system, and involved use of logarithms.

Logarithmic calculations using tables were also developed during this time. The essential structure of these computational uses can be viewed in the perspectives described below.

Abstract forms

Logarithmic and trigonometric tables were used in computational contexts in accordance with the following abstract scheme:

- Problem: Compute the function $f: R^n \mapsto R$ at $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in R^n$ subject to additional constraints.
- Step-1: Form a function $g \circ f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ and simplify it. 'g' may be the identity function $gx = x$.
- Step-2: Read the value of the simplified parts from the table as per the if-then procedures.
- Step-3: Simplify
- Step-4: Transform the computed value as per suggested procedures (this may involve additional tables) and
- Step-5: Finally obtain the desired value of $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ to a degree of accuracy.

In the above, note that Step-2 also involves a search strategy. One has to visually converge to specific regions of the table to get the arguments (that may not be exact in absolute terms, but is so relative to the table). Essentially this step is about finding correct instances of an association relation between parts of the computational context and the table. Analogous aspects can be associated with Step-4.

Similar methods of computation are/were followed in contexts involving engineering and statistical tables. A clearer comparison with other types of table use can be made using this abstraction.

Tables in statistics

The history of the origin of tables for official statistics is somewhat known. At least in Europe, it can be dated to the 16th century (Lee, 1995; also <https://www.york.ac.uk/depts/maths/histstat/>).

Statistical tables arise from primary systematic sampling, other primary studies, data mining, information representation, secondary studies, and computations. The field is related to machine learning, computer science, data science and AI databases, and clear boundaries between these fields for features associated with tables are substantially different at times.

Typically, data collected in manual surveys needs to be preprocessed for storage in relational or other databases. This holds good for digital surveys that do not make use of suitable survey software. Sometimes data may need to be transcribed. The additional steps involved in these transformations can vary in complexity and the amount of decision-making required. Data from pilot studies are more likely to be harder because of the typically open-ended exploration involved. Experience in related activities can help students to develop reasoning skills in data-intensive activities and interest in related topics. Students do experience difficulty in undergraduate and higher stages of their career. This is reflected in

a number of research papers in fields involving the application of statistics of various forms. The replication crisis in certain fields may also be seen to be related to this (see for example Collaboration & Open Science, 2015).

Tables are only occasionally considered in the literature on statistics education research, and when they are then it is mostly about numeric tables, their construction, and interpretation from statistical perspectives (see for example Koschat, 2005; Pfannkuch & Wild, 2004). The five-step framework for interpreting tables and graphs in Kemp & Kissane (2010) is essentially about identifying different aspects of the table, its statistical context, quality indicators, the meaning of numbers, their differences, and identifying reasons for changes. It is intended for interpretation and not for construction or data presentation.

Tables in soft and hard computing

Softness and hardness of a computing context may or may not be expressed explicitly in data and specifically in table form. Sometimes the soft aspects are part of the interpretation aspect and sometimes these are kept in tables. Further, typically such representations can be done in a number of nonequivalent ways as for example in general rough sets. More efficient ways dependent on processing techniques may be discovered in the future – this statement should be read relative to ideas of embodied cognition rather than from static context-free perspectives. Such a state of affairs is already implicit in practices in the area, and aspects of this are explored in this section.

Data cleaning

The concept of *clean data* is always relative to the reasoning or computational context. Often more time is spent in the process of cleaning datasets than in other parts of the analysis. The result of such operations depends on loose principles, vague decisions, limited resources, familiarity with the context, and internal consistency of the dataset. Therefore, it is possible that different practitioners may produce non-unique datasets from the original.

Fixing time, for example, written in different ways in a column of a huge table may be done by actual uniformization or by eliminating entire rows that have improper formatting. Decisions relating to the scenario may have significant consequences.

While corrections of formatting inconsistency involve limited philosophical or meta-theoretic principles, situations relating to missing data, garbled data, outliers, wrong values, typos, extrapolation, supervenience, partial feature selection, partial feature extraction are very different. As a result it is not common for practitioners to arrive at similar end results after working on the same data dump – this has also to do with the lack of proper understanding of the philosophical and meta heuristics associated with the dataset in question. A substantial part of this is related to skills in reasoning with data, and their very generation or construction.

Specific problems like machine learning algorithms learning sexism, racism, and other forms of discrimination can also be said to be due to poor techniques of cleaning. Implicit in

this is the idea that a table is a form of expression (Haslanger et al., 2015; O'Neil, 2016) and not an immutable fact.

This diversity in interpretation of tables (and imperfect variations thereof) is however not matched in pedagogical practice in allied fields and should be of obvious concern.

Rules and Reasoning

A number of rules and patterns may be discovered from tables. For example,

- From a table of marks or grades obtained by class-X students in different subjects it may be deduced that *those with marks in the range [78, 99] in mathematics obtain at least 60 marks in physics*.
- From an instance of a few winning positions in a game of four-in-a-row, basic rules of the game maybe deduced. In fact, it is possible to find all possible winning combinations for a fixed table size.
- From a multiplication table of integers, some additional information about addition may be deduced. In fact additional rules depend on the language used at the meta level.

Because many of the rules discovered, and associated reasoning can be junk, finding appropriate ones requires considerable understanding of the context and application in the tabular framework. It can be argued that an early introduction to such reasoning can be useful for developing skills in rule discovery.

Abstract representations

The concept of information can also be defined in many not necessarily equivalent ways. In Mani (2020), the present author defined information as anything that alters or has the potential to alter a given context in a significant positive way within a semantic domain. This is among the most general definitions of the concept and can be related to interconnections between properties, discernibility and identity of objects. More specifically, a set of properties Q supervene on another set of properties T in a domain of discourse if there exist no two objects of the domain that differ on Q without differing on T. Let T be a set of mental properties, Q a set of physical properties, and the domain of discourse be restricted to some species. If the physical indiscernibility of any two entities relative to Q implies their mental indiscernibility relative to T, then Q supervenes on T.

Specific fields like general rough sets may impose additional conditions on the concept of information mentioned such as the possession of the property to potentially modify supervenience relations in the contexts, and of having formalizable approximations. While the concept of an information table (described below) as used in rough sets encodes a very special case of the above situation, it is nevertheless useful to capture all ideas of what a table might be.

In an information table, row names correspond to *objects*, column names to *attributes* and cell entries to *values assigned to the object-attribute pair*. This scheme works for all cases

including frequency, and contingency tables, and tables with complex partitions of columns or rows after a level. The last case does require some reformulation.

An *information table* \mathcal{J} , is a tuple of the form $\mathcal{J} = \langle \mathcal{D}, \mathbb{A}, \{V_a : a \in \mathbb{A}\}, \{f_a : a \in \mathbb{A}\} \rangle$ with \mathcal{D} , \mathbb{A} and V_a being respectively sets of *Objects*, *Attributes*, and *Values* respectively. $f_a : \mathcal{D} \mapsto \wp(V_a)$ being the valuation map associated with attribute $a \in \mathbb{A}$. Values may also be denoted by the binary function $v : \mathbb{A} \times \mathcal{D} \mapsto \wp(V)$ defined by for any $a \in \mathbb{A}$ and $x \in \mathcal{D}$, $v(a, x) = f_a(x)$.

An information table \mathcal{J} is said to *deterministic* if and only if each object-attribute pair is associated with a singleton (that is essentially with a single value). In symbols,

It is said to be *indeterministic* $(\forall a \in \mathbb{A})(\forall x \in \mathcal{D})f_a(x)$ is a singleton (or incomplete) if it is not deterministic that is $(\exists a \in \mathbb{A})(\exists x \in \mathcal{D})f_a(x)$ is not a singleton.

In Table 3, some information concerning evaluation of activities done by students in a class is tabulated. The table is complete, and it may be noted that the objects, attributes and associated value sets are as below. If the table is read in the default perspective, then student **F** obtained a **A+** grade. **{E, F, C, K, L}** is the set of objects, **{Name, Novelty, Effort, Connections, Grade}** the set of attributes, and **{Medium, High, OK, Mild, A, A+, B+, 0, 1}** the set of values.

Name	Novelty	Effort	Model	Connections	Grade
E	Medium	Medium	1	OK	B+
F	High	OK	1	High	A+
C	High	Medium	0	Low	A
K	Medium	OK	1	OK	B+
L	High	Low	1	High	A+

Table 3: Activity Evaluation

Two-valued relations from a finite set F to another finite set K can be represented as Boolean matrix or as a table with entries being pairs of subsets of F and K in particular. Relations can also be derived from information tables through conditions of the following form: For any $x, w \in \mathcal{D}$ and a subset B of \mathbb{A} , x is σ -related to w if and only if $(\mathbf{Q}a, b \in B)\Phi(v(a, x), v(b, w),)$ for some quantifier \mathbf{Q} and formula Φ . The formulation is very general and a number of conditions can be written in the form. In symbols, $(\forall x, w \in \mathcal{D})(\forall B \subseteq \mathbb{A})\sigma xw \leftrightarrow (\mathbf{Q}a, b \in B)\Phi(v(a, x), v(b, w),)$.

Other n-place relations and partial relations are also definable through extended versions of the formulas (including Boolean combinations and others). However, in practice most people do not bother to define or involve themselves with relatively complex formulas. *This contributes adversely to the quality of analysis in a number of situations including sociological ones.* Examples of such relations can be found in (Mani, 2018).

The point of this section is to assert that a wide spectrum of reasoning is possible naturally under minimal assumptions from tables. This increases dramatically when ideas of approximation or multi-valued or dialectical truth are brought in or when reasoning is

focused on mereological considerations. While such properties may be found in other classes of expression, they lack the deceptive simplicity and context relatedness of tables.

While the point of open-ended tasks (as specified in Yeo, 2015) in tabular frameworks can be argued for from examples such as those considered in Raval et al. (2020), a clearer understanding of the possibilities can be obtained from the abstractions of this section.

Math anxiety and tables

In the context of math anxiety, studies prove partly that in assessment situations, the internalized stereotype affects the perception of task difficulty and is related to increased strain and tension as well as decreased performance (Ertl et al., 2017; Luttenberger et al., 2018). Further over the course of childhood, this leads to avoidance of math, harmful learning behaviors, and lower performance. This is because the latter problem is typically associated with fear of the mathematical (whatever the cause may be). But the person experiencing math anxiety cannot be expected to experience it over the entire spectrum of mathematical activities. A complex geometrical problem that requires knowledge of trigonometry may induce far more anxiety than a study of tabular information. In other words, key parts of math anxiety refer to anxiety in the context of specific types of mathematics. Confidence in specific parts of mathematics can potentially help in overcoming the problem gradually. For these reasons open-ended study of different types of tables can be useful for eliminating math anxiety in people. While empirical studies supporting this very specific claim are wanting, closely related studies warrant it.

Bruner's (1961) framework, in particular, relates to the observation that if students learn to obtain knowledge of a subject through the use of their own mind, then they are likely to learn best. At a methodological level, in the context of math method courses in teacher training, this can be about emphasis on the use of manipulatives and concrete learning of the mathematical content, journal logs, small and whole group instruction and presentations, literature based activities, and practical experiences. A number of empirical studies (like Gresham, 2007) show that math anxiety can be reduced in math teachers through such a framework. Specifically, tables are regarded as commonplace objects that are everywhere. So they are unlikely to cause any additional anxiety when used in the situations mentioned, and can actually facilitate the mentioned methodology especially in the light of the possibilities discussed in this paper.

More for a consistent table pedagogy

Tables are typically deceptively simple and potentially hide a large amount of information. Discovery (or invention) of such information can involve a wide assortment of techniques that are used in multiple branches of science. From the overview of table use in different disciplines a critical understanding of what might be a consistent choice of goals for open-ended tasks can be indicated, and a well-designed diverse curriculum can help in appreciation of techniques and reasoning skills involved.

Data science, machine learning, soft computing, and AI are all used in diverse fields from relatively exact applied fields to the social sciences. But key skills relating to use of tables are not commonly taught in schools. This results in so-called skilled people mangling or distorting data during the data cleaning process. It is also often the case that such acts are not detected by anybody in associated work groups.

People in different walks of life use tables frequently. Typically, such usage is focused on the task at hand. For example, a Uber driver may keep track of time, earnings, and distance using tables on a notebook to keep a tab on any cheating by the parent company. But the driver may not bother to construct an improved table (or analyze the table in a way) that can potentially improve their own quality of life in additional ways. Apparently such restricted mindsets are likely constructed in some classrooms.

Conclusion

Teaching tables in relatively open-ended ways from lower classes can be most useful to foster critical thinking and promote smoother concept maturation over time. In this research a number of pointers to potential thrust areas, and the scope of such actions is explored, and further research is naturally motivated. It is also argued that an improved, broader approach to tables may help in reducing math anxiety of learners and teachers. The practice of *table study* can be a new subject essential to the practice of the relatively more exact, and inexact sciences. *Most importantly it is not restricted by specific viewpoints and is adaptable to multiple languages in both formal and less formal senses.*

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References

- Alberich, R., Burmeister, P., Rossello, F., Valiente, G., & Wojdylo, B. (1994). A partial algebras approach to graph transformation. In J. Cuny, H. Ehrig, G. Engels & G. Rozenberg (Eds.), *Graph Grammars and their Application to Computer Science* 5th International Workshop, Springer Verlag, Chapter 1, 1-15.
- Bruner, J. (1961). *The process of education*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Burkhardt, H., Seibt, J., Imaguire, G., & Gerogiorgakis, S. (2017). *Handbook of mereology*. Philosophia Verlag, Germany.
- Chajda, I., Langer, H., & Sevcik, P. (2015). An Algebraic Approach to Binary Relations. *Asian European J. Math* 8, 2, 1-13.
- Collaboration, Open Science. (2015). Estimating the reproducibility of psychological science. *Science* 349, 6251, 1–8. OSF. <https://osf.io/82fth>
- Dowker, A., Sarkar, A., & Looi, C. (2016). Mathematics anxiety: What have we learned in 60 years? *Frontiers in Psychology* 7, 508–528. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00508>
- Ertl, B., Luttenberger, S. & Paechter, M. (2017). The impact of gender stereotypes on the self-concept of female students in stem subjects with an under-representation of females. *Frontiers in Psychology* 8, 703-718.

- Gresham, G. (2007). A study of mathematics anxiety in pre-service teachers, *Early Childhood Education Journal*, Vol. 35, No. 2, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-007-0174-7>
- Haslanger, S., Tuana, N., & O'Connor, P. (2015). Topics in feminism. In E. Zalta (Ed.) *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (fall edition). <https://stanford.library.usyd.edu.au/archives/fall2015/entries/feminism-topics/>
- Kemp, M., & Kissane, B. (2010). A five-step framework for interpreting tables and graphs in their contexts In C. Reading (Ed.), *Data and context in statistics education: Towards an evidence-based society*. Proceedings of ICOTS-8, Ljubljana, Slovenia. Voorburg, The Netherlands: ISI
- Koschat, M. A. (2005). A case for simple tables, *The American Statistician*, 59:1, 31-40, <https://doi.org/10.1198/000313005X21429>
- Lee, P. (1995). *The history of statistics - A select bibliography* (second ed.), University of York.
- Luttenberger, S., Wimmer, S., & Paechter, M. (2018). Spotlight on math anxiety. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management* 11, 311-322.
- Magnus, P. D., Button, T., Loftis, J., Trueman, R., Thomas-Bolduc, & A., Zach, R. (2020). *For All X* (fall 2020 ed.). University of Calgary. <https://forallx.openlogicproject.org/>
- Mani, A. (2016). Algebraic semantics of proto-transitive rough sets. *Transactions on Rough Sets XX, LNCS 10020*, 51-108.
- Mani, A. (2018). Algebraic methods for granular rough sets. In A. Mani, I. Düntsch, and G. Cattaneo (Eds.), *Algebraic methods in general rough sets*, Birkhauser Basel, 157-336.
- Mani, A. (2020). Comparative approaches to granularity in general rough sets. In R. Bello, D. Miao, R. Falcon, M. Nakata, A. Rosete, & D. Ciucci (Eds.), *IJCRS 2020, LNAI, Vol. 12179*. Springer, 500-518. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-52705-1>
- Mani, A., & Radeleczki, S. (2020). Algebraic approach to directed rough sets. ArXiv. Math 2004.12171, 1-37. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2004.12171>
- O'Neil, C. (2016). *Weapons of math destruction: How big data increases inequality and threatens democracy*. Crown.
- Pfannkuch, M. & Wild, C. (2004). Towards an understanding of statistical thinking In D. Ben-Zvi and J. Garfield (eds.), *The challenge of developing statistical literacy, reasoning and thinking*, 17-46, Academic Publishers.
- Pino-Fan, L., Guzmán, I., Duval, R., & Font, V. (2015). The theory of registers of semiotic representation and the onto-semiotic approach In K. Beswick, T. Muir, & J. Fielding-Wells (Eds.). *Proc. of 39th Psychology of Mathematics Education conference*, Vol. 4, 33-40. Hobart, Australia: PME.
- Raval, H., Kanhere, A., & Subramanian, J. (2020). Mathematical explorations encouraging mathematical processes in a classroom. In K. K. Mashood, T. Sengupta, C. Ursekar, H. Raval & S. Dutta (Eds.), *epiSTEME 8, HBCSE, TIFR, Mumbai*, 378-387.
- Rosenfield, B. A. (1988). *A history of non-euclidean geometry*. 471 pp. Springer-Verlag, Heidelberg.
- Swerdlow, N. W. (2000). Kepler's iterative solution to Kepler's equation. *Journal of the History of Astronomy* 31, 4 (2000), 339-41.
- Yeo, J. W. (2015). Developing a framework to characterise the openness of mathematical tasks. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education* 15, 1 (2015), 175-191.
- Zinner, E. (1990). *Regiomontanus: life and work*. North Holland, Amsterdam.